

ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS GROUP

NEWSLETTER

MARCH 1993

The Institute of Physics

Environmental Physics Group Committee

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Mr Peter Hughes	Science Dept Kingsway College
Dr Alastair McCartney	Plant Pathology Dept Rothamsted Experimental Station
Dr Douglas Peirson	formerly Environmental and Medical Sciences Dept Harwell
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Dr John Stewart	Remote Sensing Application Section Institute of Hydrology
Dr Anne Wheldon	Energy Group, Dept of Engineering University of Reading
Professor Edward Youngs	Silsoe College Cranfield Institute of Technology
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The EPG: a view as it heads towards its second AGM

At our Annual General Meeting in May 1992, I was succeeded as Chairman of the Environmental Physics Group by Professor Mike Unsworth. In October, Mike left the UK for the States, and I found myself standing in until a new election at our next AGM. Meanwhile our best wishes go to Mike in his appointment as Director of the Centre for Analysis and Environmental Change, Oregon State University.

Once again, many thanks are due to Alastair McCartney, our Honorary Secretary, without whose sterling efforts the EPG would still be at the drawing board.

Much of the time and energy spent by your committee goes towards the discussion and organisation of scientific meetings. Constructive and practical suggestions from EPG members would certainly aid and improve our efforts. It is worth emphasising that meetings are by no means restricted to the London IOP headquarters. Indeed, we are keen to promote activities elsewhere. Such meetings can be proposed in conjunction with a local IOP branch and / or university. The latter case, given a student audience, could be particularly worthwhile. Many at that stage in their scientific careers are unaware of the primary role physics plays in environmental science. *We look forward to your suggestions!*

Another less well known function of the committee of the EPG is the allocation of members for the CSTI Advisory Committee on the Environment. The CSTI (the Council of Science and Technology Institutes) represents the major professional institutions and learned societies, providing, as one of their activities, advice to government and public bodies on a number of topics. These can be in addition to individual body's own responses, and tends to be when a combined response is felt either desirable or preferable.

Other CSTI initiatives included the Environmental Information Paper on the Greenhouse Effect mentioned in the previous newsletter. This contained a substantial contribution from the IOP through the efforts of Susanna Lithiby. This issue of the newsletter is being produced by both Susanna and Dr Geoff Hassall, Oxford University's Dept of Engineering Science, since Susanna has recently left the IOP. This gives me the opportunity to both welcome Dr Hassall, and record our thanks to Susanna for the many services - not just editing the newsletter - given to the EPG since its inception. We wish her well.

Douglas Peirson
Acting Chairman

January 1993

Committee News

Annual General Meeting 29 April 1993

The second AGM of the Group will be held on 29th April at 47 Belgrave Square, London. Following on the success of last year's AGM, it will start at 6 pm, and followed straight after by a guest speaker. This year we are delighted that Dr John Woods, Director of Marine and Atmospheric Sciences at the Natural Environment Research Council has agreed to speak at 6.30 pm. Following the lecture there will be an opportunity to enjoy a glass of wine. Further details will be announced in due course.

Members are reminded that if they wish to bring forward business of a character suitable for consideration at the meeting they should give notice in writing to the Honorary Secretary at least four weeks before the AGM.

There are two vacancies for Ordinary Members of the Committee arising from the resignation of Professor Unsworth and Dr Coffee. Nominations for Officers (Chairman, Vice-Chairman and Honorary Secretary) and for Ordinary Members of the Committee should be proposed by **not less than two** Members of the Group and should be accompanied by the written consent of the nominee. Nominations should reach the Honorary Secretary **not less than seven days** before the AGM.

The Committee's nominations for Officers and Ordinary Members are:

Chairman: Dr John Stewart, Institute of Hydrology, Wallingford
Vice-Chairman: Dr Douglas Peirson, ex AEA Harwell
Honorary Secretary: Dr Alastair McCartney, AFRC, IACR, Rothamsted
Ordinary Members: Dr Neil Roberts, Magnetic Resonance Research Centre, Liverpool
Dr Geoff Hassall, Department of Engineering Science, Oxford

Non-resigning Ordinary Members*:

Mr Graham Alcock	Dr Peter Dagley
Professor John Harries	Mr Peter Hughes
Dr Ranjeet Sokhi	Dr Anne Wheldon
Dr Edward Youngs	

* see current committee list for affiliations

Register of Members' Interests

Members may recall that we circulated a request for information on members' expertise with a previous newsletter. You will find this enclosed once more, and can I ask everyone who has not returned a form to Ranjeet Sokhi to help us by doing so this time? The information will be used to help target EPG activities, and will be freely available to all.

The EPG needs you! a plea for help with evening meetings

The Committee would like to hold evening meetings, similar to those held by local IOP branches, as a regular feature of the EPG's programme. The meetings would focus on particular environmental problems or topics and be structured to include debate as well as information exchange. The venues of these meetings would vary, but as Douglas highlighted in his editorial, would preferably be in Universities and Colleges, perhaps in collaboration with student Physical Societies. We would like the meeting to be aimed at undergraduates, postgraduates and possibly local school students, the overall aim being to highlight the importance of physics in understanding and solving environmental problems. If you feel you could help organise such a meeting, or if you are prepared to act as a speaker, or if you have any suggestions for meeting topics, please **DO** contact me. The EPG is what **you** make it!

Alastair McCartney, Honorary Secretary

A bit of background on our new Newsletter Editor

Geoff Hassall studied theoretical physics at the University of York and graduated in 1984. He went on to study aspects of the science and applications of electric plasmas in the Department of Engineering Science at Oxford. After completing a MSc and a DPhil he went on to post-doctoral work in the Low Temperature Plasma Department of the Culham Laboratory and in the Engineering Laboratory at Oxford. During 1992 he began work relating to environmental applications of gas discharges. This became full-time in December when he began investigating atmospheric and super-atmospheric pulsed electrical discharges in the detoxification of gaseous waste streams. He has wide interests in the development and implementation of environmental technology and renewable energy systems and in the evolution of world-wide governmental policy and its impact on both industrial and academic environmental research.

Forthcoming Meetings

See also insert with this newsletter, relating to *The Physics of Plant Environments*, 13 May.

Is Green Clean?

24 February 1993 Society of Chemical Industry, 14/5 Belgrave Square,, London

The revised Montreal Protocol (1990) commits nations to cease usage of ozone-depleting chemicals by the end of the century. To this end EC regulations will demand a reduction in CFC consumption by 85% of the 1986 level before the end of 1993 and complete phase-out by the end of 1995. These and other closely related chemicals form the backbone of many cleaning processes for vacuum purposes. Invited speakers at this one-day discussion meeting will include an expert on the Montreal Protocol, representatives of the chemical and cleaning industries and users.

Contact: Meetings Dept, IOP, 47 Belgrave Square, London SW1X 8QX

Aerobiology and Agriculture

24 March 1993 Rothamsted Experimental Station, Harpenden Herts

This is the inaugural scientific meeting of the British Aerobiology Federation, whose President is Professor J M Hirst FRS. Topics to be included are aerobiology at Rothamsted, changing patterns of grassland and crop utilisation in relation to airborne pollens and spores, pollens and spore dispersal from cops and airborne spores, and occupational lung diseases.

Speakers will include J M Hirst, A Hopkins, G W Cussans, H A McCartney and B Crook.

A small number of offered papers and posters can be accepted.

Registration: £10 members, £20 non-members. Further details from Dr John Lacey, Plant Pathology Dept at the address above. Tel:0582 7631333; fax:0582 760981

Edinburgh International Science Festival

Two meetings with which the IOP have been involved are being organised at this year's Science Festival. Further information is obtained from the Edinburgh Science Festival Office, 1 Broughton Market, Edinburgh EH3 6NU; tel: 031 556 6446

Solar Energy Symposium 13 April 1993 Edinburgh

The Royal Society of Edinburgh, 22-24 George Street, Edinburgh EH2 2PQ

Jointly sponsored by IOP Environmental Physics Group, IOP Scottish Branch, & Royal Society of Edinburgh
This is a one-day meeting, following in the steps of last year's successful Environmental Physics day. The speakers are listed below and entry is free to IOP members.

Development and Applications of Photovoltaic Devices

Professor Bob Hill & Dr Nicola Pearsall, University of Northumbria

Commercial Development of Photovoltaic Devices Dr Tim Bruton, BP Solar Ltd

Thermal Solar Power Mr Kerr MacGregor, Napier University

Solar Energy: A Scottish Perspective

Dr John Twidell, Strathclyde University

Wood Biofuels

Dr Paul Mitchell, Aberdeen University

Chemical Photosynthesis and Storage

Dr Ian Dunkin, Strathclyde University

Organiser: Mr Alan Harper, Chairman IOP Scottish Branch; tel 0324 494074

The internal combustion engine and the urban environment: are present controls adequate? 14 April 1993 Royal College of Physicians, Edinburgh Entry: £2 / £1 concessions

This day-long debate, organised by the CSTI Advisory Committee on the Environment, of which the IOP is a member, will include representatives from Transport 2000, Friends of the Earth, Vauxhall Motors and the British Medical Journal.

British Soil Water Physics Group 5 May 1993

A workshop on the measurement of soil water using time domain reflectometry is to be held at the Silsoe Research Institute, Wrest Park, Silsoe, Beds, MK45 4HS.

tel: 0525 86000; fax 0525 860156

Wind and wind-related damage to trees

18 - 23 July Heriot Watt University, Scotland

Members of the organising committee include representatives from the Forestry Commission, the Institute of Terrestrial Ecology and the University of Edinburgh.

Further details can be obtained from the Chairman of the Organising Committee, C P Quine, Forestry Commission, Northern Research Station, Roslin, Midlothian, Scotland EH25 9SY; tel: 031 445 2176; fax: 031 445 5124

International Tyndall School 11 - 19 September 1993 Carlow, Ireland

A meeting to celebrate the centenary of the death of John Tyndall FRS (1820-93). Tyndall was a man gifted in many areas. As well as being a nineteenth century "environmental scientist", he was a pioneer of monitoring equipment for air and water. He was a close collaborator of Pasteur and a founding father of bacteriology.

The Institute of Physics and the Environmental Physics Group are two of many organisations sponsoring this event, which includes a major environmental conference, plus a number of Radon Day Schools for schools and the public. The event will be launched with a Royal Institution discourse in London, and will include a number of cultural as well as scientific events.

A full programme is available from Dr Norman McMillan, Carlow Resource Centre, tel: 010 353 503 32218; fax: 010 353 503 43787

Inland and Water Quality '93 Warren Spring Laboratory September 1993

details of this meeting have already been circulated to EPG members

Further information from the IOP Meetings Dept

News, reviews and other information

GER Directory

The UK GER Office is jointly funded by the five UK research councils and has recently published *The International Directory of Global Environmental Research*. This gathers together information regarding international initiatives, programmes and organisations involved with environmental research. It is intended as a useful guide for those working in the environmental area, and provides an insight into the international effort, the activities and - more importantly perhaps - a knowledge of how the organisations included in this directory are interlinked and how they interact with each other.

The directory has five main sections under the following headings:

- 1) Inter-governmental organisations/programmes
- 2) International non-governmental organisations
- 3) Proposed Global Observing Systems
- 4) Major International Science Programmes
- 5) Other Mechanisms for GER coordination

In each case, the detailed objectives of each organisation, programme or programmes are stated clearly and a relevant contact point is given.

Copies are available from:

UK GER Office,
Polaris House,
North Star Avenue,
Swindon SN2 1EU
Tel: (0793) 411734

Fax: (0793) 411691

The Globe

The latest issue of the *Globe* has just appeared. This very informative publication is available from the address above.

The February issue contains an update on the START programme, whose aim is to establish a global system of research networks to stimulate research on global environmental change. A secretariat has been established, with Professor Thomas Rosswall as acting Executive Director.

Articles also appear on the Climate Change Programme at the AFRC Institute of Grassland and Environmental Research, the Hadley Centre - Lancaster University Centre for the Study of Environmental Change project looking at the construction and development of global climate models and their use in policy making, a report on the SERC discussion on its involvement in UK global environmental change research, plus its normal conference round-up and exhaustive list of meeting and conference dates.

Infoterra

INFOTERRA was established in 1975 as an international mechanism for the exchange of environmental information and since then it has grown to become one of the largest environmental information supply systems in the world. It has national focal points in 137 countries and these, together with the Programme Activity Centre at the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) headquarters in Nairobi, provide environmental information vital for better decision making and for better environmental protection. It provides a pool of knowledge for governments, industry and researchers alike responding to specific enquiries by providing raw information or by establishing links between enquirers and the experts. INFOTERRA is an integral part of UNEP and is guided by, and receives its mandate from, the UNEP Governing Council.

Further information about the Infoterra network can be obtained from:

INFOTERRA Programme Activity Centre,
United Nations Environment Programme,
P.O. Box 30552,
Nairobi KENYA
Tel: (254-2) 333 930
Fax: (254-2) 520711

Environmental Information Handbook

PIRA's International Environmental Information Source is a publication providing international coverage of sources of environmental information. Key environmental topics are covered, e.g. air, noise, water and land pollution; waste control and disposal; recycling; energy recovery; and nature conservation. Entries from more than 20 countries are included covering organisations, research centres, legislative/regulatory bodies, directories, statistics, online databases and periodicals.

Further details are available from PIRA, Publications Dept, Randalls Road, Leatherhead, Surrey;
tel: 0372 376161; fax: 0372 360104

DOE/DOT publication

The word is out that the library of the Department of Environment and the Department of Transport may be putting together a guide of sources of information on environmental protection which should be published this year.

International Environment, '93

International Environment '93 and *Analysis '93* will be held at the Wembley Exhibition and Conference Centre on the 11, 12 and 13 May 1993. This is its thirteenth year and the conferences and exhibition are directed at the scientific community seeking practical solutions to environmental problems. They offer a comprehensive range of subject areas that should cater for most requirements. The organisers anticipate interest from a wide range of environmental professionals, from those involved in research, to health officers

and inspectors, to the policy makers and legislators. Each session is individually charged thereby allowing a greater element of flexibility. The preliminary programme is now available with the final version offering over 250 presentations with comprehensive poster sessions to be announced in March.

Further details can be obtained from:

Labmate Ltd.,
12 Alban Park,
Hatfield Road,
St. Albans,
Herts AL4 0JJ
Tel: (0727) 55574

Fax: (0727) 41694

Implementing the Rio Agenda: Partnerships for change

Some of you will be familiar with the term "sustainable development" and the concepts that such a simple phrase implies. The UK government is to host an international conference in Manchester in late September this year which will enable voluntary branches, local government, business and industry to exchange experience in the practical implementation of sustainable development. It is intended that this conference will be part of an on-going process of implementing the agreements made at the Rio summit last year in all parts of the world.

It will include plenary meetings and workshop sessions as well as opportunities for organisations to present their activities and possibilities for visiting environment projects in the UK.

Further details will be available later but comments and indications of interest should be sent to:

Craig Jones
Department of the Environment
Room A305,
Romney House,
43 Marsham St.,
London SW1P 3PY
Tel: (071) 276 8843

Fax: (071) 276 8861

Draft UK VOC Strategy Document

In recent years there has been a rapid growth in interest in controlling industrial emissions of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), ie solvents. Legislation on both national and international levels has led to a pan-European protocol which the UK government has signed and is due to ratify later this year. Action to control VOCs emissions is being coordinated internationally within both the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and the European Community (EC). In a response to this, the UK Department of Environment issued a consultation document setting out the action being taken in the UK as part of these international efforts and in particular to meet obligations agreed under the UNECE protocol in 1991.

Although the deadline for responses to the consultation document has passed (15 January, 1993), the DoE anticipate issuing a final version of this document by the end of March this year. It will form an inventory of current VOCs emissions, their sources and the actions that can be taken to limit their release into the environment although it will not be a definitive statement of government policy. By 1999 it has been agreed that VOCs emissions must have been reduced by 30% from their 1988 levels and this document will detail how this can be done.

My copy of the consultation document has 10 chapters and annexes totaling some 45 pages, together with technical annexes totaling 97 pages. A list of those companies and organisations consulted is also included.

This text will provide an extensive "snap-shot" of the current state of VOCs emissions in this country and should go on the reading list of anyone interested in the air we breath.

Further information can be obtained from:

Air Quality Division,
Department of the Environment,
Romney House,
43 Marsham St.,
London SW1P 3PY
Tel: (071) 276 8197

The Chemical Engineer.

For those of us interested in how the Environmental Protection Act has influenced industry I should refer readers to an environmental supplement of The Chemical Engineer (29 October, 1992). Six articles report on the implications of the new legislation, how it is being implemented by industry, how they are being monitored and what effect is it having. Subjects include (using TCE contents notes):

- 1) Progress and Politics - Coping with integrated pollution control so far, and advice on how to survive the future.
- 2) The Right to Know - Will going public with emissions figures improve the process industries' image ?
- 3) Contamination Land - The implications for the UK and some US experience. 4) Environmental Auditing - Getting to grips with BS7750 and eco-auditing.
- 5) Pollution Prevention - A roundup of selected techniques for cleaning up.
- 6) Information on Technologies - A useful list of information sources.

reviews done by Geoff Hassall

A view from the front line

I think you will all agree that this is an exciting time to be involved in environmental research and I am pleased to have been given the opportunity of taking over as editor of the EPG newsletter. My own research work is heavily oriented towards environmental matters and considers how high pressure electrical discharges can be used to control hazardous gaseous emissions. As you would imagine, this has both a heavy environmental and commercial bias. Those of you who read the article by Graeme Lister in the December issue of *Physics World* ("Plasmas join the fight against acid rain", p19) will have some idea of what I'm talking about.

Current thinking about pollution control focuses on so-called "Clean Technology" and recent government initiatives have tried to encourage low waste techniques by considering the environmental impact of industrial production and including attempts to minimise input raw materials, general waste minimisation through recycling and resource recovery, and the development of efficient waste management technologies and techniques. A broader range of industries, involving smaller companies, are being affected and must comply with the ever stricter national and international emissions regulations, often with equipment and know-how developed when such matters were hardly considered. Add to that the current world economic climate and one can see that we have a serious challenge awaiting us.

Care must be taken in implementing such standards. Whilst regulation plays an important role in driving technological progress, if it is imposed too rapidly then corners will be cut and legal loop-holes will be exploited. As scientists our purpose is manifold. We are here to help industry find solutions to these practical problems, to help the public understand what the problems are and what we can do about them, but perhaps most importantly, we should be keeping both sides in touch with the facts and with each other. This is done through careful monitoring, assessing impartially and objectively how the impact that industry is having on the environment.

The newsletter is here to disseminate information, to help physicists of all descriptions be aware that they can contribute to an inherently multi-disciplinary problem. I want to continue to provide the membership with an effective information service which reflects not only the views of the committee, but yours as well and, if possible, to respond through the newsletter to your comments, opinions and suggestions.

Geoff Hassall